

Changing Teaching Practice to Support Spatial Skills Development in Primary School Children in Ireland

Angela Langan

Dublin City University

Spatial skills are strongly correlated with achievement in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and are also intrinsic in other curricular areas. Emerging research suggests that interventions aimed at building students' spatial skills may yield significant impacts on learning in educational settings (Gagnier & Fisher, 2020). Yet, despite this the intentional practice of teaching spatial thinking skills is largely absent in school curriculums. The aim of this research was to explore changing teaching practice to support the spatial skills development of primary school children in Ireland. It also aimed to examine how to leverage aspects of the Knowledge Transfer Framework (Gagnier & Fisher, 2020) to help infuse spatial skills into lessons, changed and informed practice. Key spatial enhancements were integrated into three lessons across the curriculum. An action research method focusing on a group of six primary school students (age 7-8 years) within the whole class setting was used. The findings of this research conclude that children benefit and respond positively to the spatially-enhanced lessons and it is possible to infuse spatial enhancements into lessons whilst meeting the objectives of the Irish Primary School Curriculum.

Keywords: Spatial skills, enhancements, integration, cross-curricular

Introduction

Spatial skills help individuals read maps, interpret charts, assemble furniture, visualise things we cannot see and aid us to represent these things in the mind, through drawing, construction, gesture and language. These foundational skills that start developing in early life have been found to contribute to children's learning and success in STEM and other areas such as the arts and physical education. Yet, despite this the intentional practice of teaching spatial thinking skills is largely absent in school curricula. The lack of focus in teaching and curricula in fostering spatial skills means we risk losing a significant cohort of potentially talented individuals (OECD, 2017). Spatial skills are associated with STEM careers and explicit attention to assessing and developing spatial skills may support teachers in identifying children with high spatial skills who might not be identified on other traditional achievement measures. Supporting spatial skills development in schools may also help under-represented groups gain access to STEM careers.

Literature

Existing literature, including meta-analyses of longitudinal studies over the last 50 years evidences the role and importance of spatial skills development in STEM and lifelong career achievement (Lowrie & Jorgensen, 2017). While early studies in this area sometimes focused on gender or 'natural ability' it is generally accepted that spatial skills are malleable through appropriate intentional interventions and experience (Cheng & Mix, 2014).

While some differences in achievement are noted across gender it appears likely these arise due to social and educational factors and will require a system-wide support structure from educational curriculum and practitioners, parents and other individual factor levels to combat stereotyping and cultural factors to promote and foster spatial skills and STEM interest in girls (Andrews et al., 2016; Clerkin & Perkins, 2019). Literature indicates that individuals from a

lower socioeconomic background tend to fare less well on spatial ability skills and academic achievement but with appropriate interventions to support their development, these skills may partially or fully improve (Lowrie & Jorgensen, 2017).

The difficulties of incorporating spatial skills development in an already crowded curriculum and the ensuing call from scientists to spatialise the curriculum have been noted in a range of international and national literature (Irish Primary Principals Network, 2017; National Research Council Of The National Academies, 2005; NCCA, 2010; Ministry of Education Ontario, 2014; OECD, 2017). The Knowledge Transfer Framework (Gagnier & Fisher, 2020) is an example of how to translate scientific knowledge into educational curriculum and practice. While there is little explicit reference to spatial skills in Irish policy documents, proposed changes to curriculum align with the recommendations arising from international literature. Ireland has already taken steps to increase the focus on spatial skills development in children through the revision of the Draft Primary Mathematics Curriculum (NCCA, 2022) and the augmentation of the Shape and Space Strand and the integrated approach to teaching and learning in the proposed Draft Primary Curriculum (NCCA, 2022).

Methodology

The aim of this study was to explore how spatial enhancements might be incorporated into the Irish primary school curriculum subjects of Social, Environmental and Science Education (SESE), Mathematics and Art lessons and to investigate children's responses to spatially-enhanced lessons using an integrated cross-curricular approach. The research entailed observation of a focus group of six students from 2nd class aged 7-8 years, of mixed ability and gender. It leveraged aspects of the Knowledge Transfer Framework (KTF) developed by Gagnier and Fisher (2020) to teach lessons using five key spatial enhancement skills of Visualization Instruction, Sketching, Spatial Comparison, Spatial Language and Gesture.

The KTF draws upon research from cognitive, developmental, educational and implementation sciences to guide the infusion of spatial-thinking into a curriculum intervention. The framework offers practical advice on how to purposefully plan and infuse these spatial thinking skills into curriculum areas for both teacher and students to apply in teaching and learning. Leveraging and adapting the KTF with the Irish Primary School Curriculum learning objectives in mind, the lessons were purposefully designed using a cross-curricular integrated approach on the theme of Explorers to include spatial enhancements scaffolded by the teacher and subsequent spatially-enhanced student activities for children to respond and actively engage in the lessons. Figure 1 below provides an overview of these lessons.

Figure 1

Overview of Lessons

Lessons	Key Activities	Cross Curricular Integration
Lesson 1	<i>Christopher Columbus Story: Students explore and develop the language of spatial properties and relations. Students draw map of how mid-1400s Europeans would have imagined the world to look like based on spatial properties as described by teacher. Students compare to modern-day map using a Venn Diagram to capture spatial (and other) similarities and differences. Students identify where Spain is on the map and in groups trace the route creating an old-world map.</i>	<p>History: Story, Change and Continuity Strand Units: Stories, Continuity and Change in the Local environment</p> <p>Geography: Natural Environments Strand Units: Planet Earth in space</p> <p>Mathematics: Data Strand Units: Representing and interpreting data</p> <p>Art: Paint and colour, Drawing</p> <p>Strand Units: Painting, Making Drawings</p>
Lesson 2	<i>Students explore and develop spatial awareness of cardinal directions and map work skills through pair/group work activities. Students introduced to the compass, map skills following and giving direction instructions and drawing a simple classroom map using keys/legends.</i>	<p>Geography: Natural Environments, Human Environments Strand Units: Planet Earth in space, Living in the Local Community</p> <p>Mathematics: Shape Strand Units: Spatial Awareness</p> <p>History: Strand: Story, Change and Continuity Strand Units: Stories, Continuity and change in the local environment</p>
Lesson 3	<i>Students complete a step-by-step activity that leads students through the process of building a boat. Collaboratively work and brainstorm the design/sketch/build of the boat, within a limited budget, Students use rich spatial language and demonstrate and explore their spatial skills in building the boat.</i>	<p>Science: Strand - Energy and forces, Materials Strand Units: Forces, Properties and characteristics of materials</p> <p>Maths: Strand - Measures Strand Units: Money, Capacity, Weight</p> <p>Art: Strand - Constructions Strand Units: Making constructions, Looking and responding</p>

An action research method was used. This involved using participant observation to explore the children’s response to spatially-enhanced lessons. McNiff (2013) states action research is always about improving learning, and improving is always to do with education and personal and professional growth. As such many people regard action research as a very powerful form of educational research. Data that was collected for this study included observation field notes, audio recordings of children’s discussions, teacher lesson plans, the teacher’s reflective journal, samples and photos of the students’ work, and students’ reflective learning logs. The data including transcriptions and pupil’s sample work were coded using a hybrid of deductive and inductive thematic analysis codes (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006). A hybrid process of deductive and inductive thematic analysis used to interpret themes from the raw data.

Findings and Analysis

Whilst these lessons were focused on the curriculum learning outcomes of History, Geography, Science, Mathematics and Visual Arts, it is clear that the intentional teaching of spatial skills using the eight spatial enhancements proposed by the KTF (Gagnier & Fisher 2020), facilitated children’s engagement in activities to meet these learning outcomes. Of paramount importance to all of the lessons is the use of spatial language as it underpins the learning throughout whether it is used on its own or in combination with another spatial activity such as gesture, sketching, comparing or visualisation. The findings of this study were amalgamated into the following themes: Responses to the Spatial Enhancements, Importance of Spatial Language, Collaborative Learning and Student Motivation. However, for the purposes of this paper, the theme of Responses to the Spatial Enhancements will be examined.

Responses to the Spatial Enhancements

As outlined, the five enhancements identified by Gagnier and Fisher (2020) include: Visualisation Instruction, Sketching, Spatial Comparison, Spatial Language and Gesture. Student activities were created that combined these various spatial enhancements and were incorporated into the lessons in fun and engaging ways. In this section, I summarise the findings of the responses categorising six of the most frequently used common student activities (*Say and Display It!*, *Diagram and Describe It!*, *Observe, Draw and Describe It!*, *Predict, Draw and Describe It!*, *Compare and Describe It!*, *Graph It!*) according to the five spatial enhancements.

Visualisation Instruction. Visualisation Instruction involves helping children to read and understand existing external representations as well as creating external representations that conveys spatial information such as maps, graphs and diagrams. Having read the story of Columbus, in lesson two the participants were tasked with creating a map depicting the route Columbus and his explorers would have taken to cross from Spain to the Caribbean. In this student activity the participants used the *Diagram and Describe It!* student activity to trace the route identifying cut outs of Europe and America, positioning them on the map and then drawing Columbus's boats showing the directionality of the route. Here to understand the process of navigation the children had to execute skill in self-location placing the three ships of the Nina, the Pinta and the Santa Maria in the middle of the Atlantic Ocean and drawing the bow of the ships in the westward direction of the Caribbean. This process effectively required the participants to initially create the map in their head of that journey and then represent it in drawing using the spatial skills of self-location and place recognition for navigational map reading (Lobben, 2007). The evidence shows this posed little difficulty for the participants although the order of the ships in the representational drawing needed to be corrected with the Santa Maria boat leading the ships to arrive first at the Caribbean.

Sketching. Research has shown sketching can facilitate reasoning and learning about spatial properties (Ainsworth et al., 2011, Nic Mhuirí, 2020). There were common student activities that included this spatial support in combination with other spatial skill-enhancements. *Diagram and Describe It!* discussed above, *Observe, Draw and Describe It!* and *Predict, Draw and Describe It!*

The student activity *Observe, Draw and Describe It!* included the sketching enhancement in combination with the use of spatial language. In lesson 2 the participants were tasked with helping Columbus discover the new land and were given a map of an island that contained symbols or keys. The participants had to follow the written instructions to locate and draw each of the symbols relative to the location of the campsite drawn on the map. It was evident from the data all participants were able to draw and describe the location of the keys on the map with ease. However, the extension activity to Map Your Own Classroom proved challenging for some participants. Data analysis showed that some children had difficulties with the concept of using keys as symbols and understanding scale and perspective. These difficulties were noted in previous research of Uttal and Sheehan (2014). A recommendation was made to provide the keys/symbols to use for the classroom map initially so that the participants could focus on the relational spatial skill as to where to draw the key on the classroom map first and then scaffold the learning until their level of understanding of the spatial relations of scales, overhead view or perspective and symbolic use of keys is developed. In lesson 3 sketching was also used to draw a

picture of their boat and label it appropriately. Here children demonstrated a good sense of space and geometry at sketching the finished boat and was comparable to the initial sketched design.

The student activity *Predict, Draw and Describe It!* includes the spatial- enhancement of sketching in combination with language. In lesson 1 the teacher described how Europeans in the mid-1400s would have imagined the world to look like using spatial language. The participants were then tasked to draw a map the way the mid-1400s Europeans would have viewed the world based on the descriptive spatial language as described by the teacher. It necessitated the participants visualising in the mind's eye according to the description and then representing it through drawing. For some participants this was a challenging task as their only concept of what the people thought the world looked like was that of the modern map displayed on the SmartScreen. Through drawing rather than writing, the children were given an opportunity to build and manipulate mental representations from a different perspective and develop their spatial thinking and reasoning skills further. Thus, they demonstrated understanding aligning with the visuo-spatial demands of science learning (Ainsworth et al., 2011; NicMhuiri, 2020).

Spatial Comparison. Comparison is particularly useful to allow learners to notice critical spatial differences between two entities (Gagnier & Fisher, 2020; Newcombe, 2010). Analogy facilitates learning through the process of comparison identifying similarities and differences between two entities. The 'Compare and Describe It!' student activity incorporates this comparison enhancement in combination with use of spatial language. As referred to earlier the student activity *Graph It!* was preceded by a scaffolded discussion by the teacher and participants to identify spatial differences between the old-world map and the modern map in lesson 1 thus sharpening the children's focus on comparing spatial properties. Most participants were able to identify key similarities and differences although it was noted that this spatial skill needed to be practised more with the children. This spatial enhancement was also used in lesson 2 as part of the *Map Your Own Classroom* student activity as described earlier in the *Observe, Draw and Describe It!* The participants swapped their maps and had to follow the direction of the keys drawn on his/her partner's map and compare it by moving in the direction the map suggested. This was challenging for half of the participants as the success of this task was dependent on the children's spatial ability to draw the map of their classroom accurately as discussed earlier. In addition, comparing the map with the physical classroom revealed that map reading requires individuals to be able relate to where you are in the real world and compare to where you are on the map when reading a map. It also involves map rotation either mentally rotating a map as you make successive turns or physically turning the map to assess direction (Lobben, 2007). Some children were observed to turn their map to go in the direction they needed to go while others displayed the ability to follow their map by being able to self-locate.

Spatial Language. Like all language learning, spatial language can influence children's spatial cognition and if developed from an early age can equip children to represent and reason about the world. This role of talk is essential in mathematical thinking and problem solving (Nic Mhuiri, 2020). Newcombe (2010) states that children that understand spatial words understand spatial relation better when it is given a name and consequently perform better on spatial tasks. As evidenced throughout this study the use of spatial language has been a fundamental cognitive tool in completing all student activities in combination with other spatial enhancements. The one exception was in lesson 3 when having completed the building of their boat and testing their boat

out in the water, the participants were tasked in step 5 of the boat building activity to reflect on the success of their boat (*Describe It!*). Prior to documenting and summarising the group's reflections in writing all participants engaged in reasoning why and why not the boat that they built was successful. Although the participants did use some spatial language using this spatial enhancement, the children's personal construction of meaning and understanding of the scientific reasons why the boat sank became most evident. However, it was noted that this assumes children have sufficient language to reason and have a good level of the English language, in particular those with English as an Additional Language (EAL) needs. In the latter case this evaluation was only made possible by the active involvement of the children in the practical and creative design and making process.

Gesture. The sole spatial enhancement that was consistently used across all lessons was the Say and Display It! spatial enhancement. This enhancement as previously discussed combines the use of language and gesture for children to describe and show their observations, experience and prediction of an activity used in the curriculum content. The evidence collected shows this is consistent with the findings of Newcombe (2010) who states children learn better when they use gesture with speech as they explain a problem. This is in contrast to just using speech alone. For example, in lesson 2, the participants had the opportunity to give evidence of their thinking by linking spatial language and representation through gesture when learning about cardinal directions. Gesture combined with spatial language provides deeper understanding and opportunity for children to develop spatial thinking skills in a meaningful way.

Significantly, the data showed that use of this spatial enhancement is useful for children in the early years who are still developing literacy skills and in particular children with EAL needs who may not have acquired sufficient language yet. This predicated with Goldin-Meadow and Alibali (2013) who argue that the act of gesturing plays a causal role in language learning by allowing children the opportunity to practise and communicate ideas they are not yet able to express in speech. Ng and Sinclair (2013) highlight the interallied role that gesture and language plays in developing mathematical thinking skills in children. One participant with EAL needs, lacked the language skills but was able to participate in the collaborative activity in lesson 3 nonetheless dually building his spatial and language skills.

Concluding Remarks

A fundamental aim of this study was to advance the research into how to spatialise the curriculum by attempting to do so with the Irish Primary School Curriculum. This was inspired by the OECD's call to governments and system leaders to recognise that spatial skills enrich the traditional educational focus on developing literacy and numeracy skills and to include this cognitive domain which is relevant to achievement in STEM and other curricular areas such as SESE and the Arts.

The findings identified opportunities for further skills development for participants particularly in the area of spatial enhancement of comparative analysis and description. From a teacher perspective this could be supported by facilitating additional and specifically focused practice lessons on this spatial skill. Factors found to challenge implementation of these lessons included supporting children with EAL needs and class size. Continued practice of collaborative

learning was identified as an opportunity for further development as is promoted by the Irish Primary School Curriculum. As the teacher assumed the role as facilitator, the participants were motivated to manage their own learning through active open-ended discovery learning.

It is noted there have been significant changes to incorporate more spatial skills development in the Draft Primary Mathematics Curriculum (NCCA, 2022). The strand of Shape and Space has been expanded with additional learning outcomes and most notably now includes the exploration and visualisation of the effects of transformation on shapes. This new emphasis in mathematics is welcome, however, it is the author's opinion that there is an opportunity to develop spatial skills in a more holistic and integrated way. This study has shown how spatial skills can be infused in the non-STEM subject areas using the eight student spatially-enhanced activities in fun and engaging ways in lessons. These spatially-enhanced student activities offer an alternative method to achieve the subject area learning outcome whilst at the same time serve to develop children's spatial skills. From experience of this study, I would argue these eight student spatially-enhanced activities can easily be put into practice and used as an additional suite of activities to design and enact teaching that will meet that objective using appropriate engaging pedagogy. This is in line with the aims of the Primary School Curriculum which supports an integrated approach to teaching and learning with links and integration across subject areas to optimise curriculum integration whilst supporting progression in learning (NCCA, 2020). Considering this and in addition, in my experience, designing these lessons presented little difficulty in accomplishing this, as the Irish primary school curriculum already encourages and promotes active open-ended discovery learning.

References

- Ainsworth, S., Prain, V., & Tytler, R. (2011). Drawing to Learn in Science. *Science Education*, 333, 1096-1097
- Cheng, Y.-L., & Kelly, M. S. (2014). Spatial Training Improves Children's Mathematics Ability. *Journal of Cognition and Development*, 15(1)
- Department of Education and Skills. (2017). *STEM Education Policy Statement 2017-2026*. Government Press.
- Fereday, J., & Muir-Cochrane, E. (2006). Demonstrating Rigour Using Thematic Analysis: A Hybrid Approach of Inductive and Deductive Coding and Theme Development. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 5(1), 80-92
- Gagnier, K. M., & Fisher, K. R. (2020, June 25). Unpacking the Black Box of Translation: A framework for infusing spatial thinking into curricula. *Cognitive Research: Principles and Implications*, 5(29)
- Goldin-Meadow, S., & Wagner Alibali, M. (2013). Gesture's role in speaking, learning, and creating language. *Annual Review Psychology*, 64, 257-283
- Irish Primary Principals Network. (2017). *IPPN Submission - STEM Education Policy*. Irish Primary Principals Network.

- Lobben, A. K. (2007). Navigational Map Reading: Predicting Performance and Identifying Relative Influence of Map-Related Abilities. *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 97(1), 64-85
- Lowrie, T., & Jorgensen, R. (2017). Equity and spatial reasoning: reducing the mathematical achievement gap in gender and social disadvantage. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 30, 65-75
- McNiff, J. (2013). *Action Research: Principles and Practice*. Routledge.
- Ministry of Education. (2014). *Paying Attention to Spatial Reasoning K12 Support Document for Paying Attention to Mathematics Education*. Ministry of Education. Ontario: Ontario Government Publications.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment. (2010). *Curriculum Overload in Primary Schools*. National Council for Curriculum and Assessment.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment. (2022). *Primary Mathematics Curriculum Draft specification for Consultation*. Government Press.
- National Research Council Of The National Academies. (2005). *Learning To Think Spatially*. National Academies Press.
- Newcombe, N. S. (2010). Picture This - Improving Maths and Science Learning by Improving Spatial Thinking. *American Educator*, 29-43
- NicMhuirí, S. (2020). *Shape and Space in the senior primary classes*. National Council for Curriculum and Assessment.
- Ng, O. L., & Sinclair, N. (2013). Gestures and temporality: Children's use of gestures on spatial transformation tasks. *Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education*. 3, pp. 361-368. A M Lindmeier, A Heinze
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2017). *Harnessing Spatial Thinking To Support STEM Learning OECD Education Working Paper No. 161*. Directorate of Education and Skills OECD. OECD.
- Perkins, R., & Clerkin, A. (2019). *TIMMS 2019 Results Ireland's Results in Mathematics and Science*. Educational Research Centre.
- Uttal, D. H., & Sheehan, K. J. (2014). The Development of Children's Understanding of Maps and Models: A Prospective Cognition Perspective. *Journal of Cognitive Education and Psychology*, 13(2), 1-13
- Uttal, D. H., & Cohen, C. A. (2012, December). Spatial thinking and STEM education: When, why and how. *Psychology of Learning and Motivation* 1, 57, 147-181